

Complex Equilibrium Studies on Aminomethylenephosphonic-*N*-carboxylic Acids with some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Complex equilibrium studies on some aminomethylenephosphonic acids like *N*-phosphonomethyliminodiacetic acid (NPMI) and *N*-phosphonomethylglycine (NPMG) for the determination of stability constants with a few bivalent metal ions, viz. Be, Zn and Cd have been carried out in an aqueous medium at 0.10 *M* (KNO₃) ionic strength and 20, 30, 40 and 50° by employing pH-metric titration techniques. NPMI forms stronger metal chelates than NPMG because of its higher basicity. The Be^{II} complexes are more stable over those of the Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes. Mixed ligand complexes involve some N-O, O-O, N-N and N-O-O donors like glycine, β-alanine, catechol, 5-sulphosalicylic acid, oxalic acid, 1,10-phenanthroline, 2,2'-bipyridyl and iminodiacetic acid. Stepwise and overall stability constants, thermodynamic parameters, differences in stabilities, percentages of relative stabilisation values and percentage of distribution of various metal chelated species have been evaluated and discussed in terms of basicity, denticity and statistical aspects of the ligands.

Schwarzenbach *et al.*¹ reported that phosphonic acid group will have an effective donor function when substituted in place of the normal carboxylic group of aminocarboxylic acids. *N*-Phosphonomethyliminodiacetic acid (NPMI) and *N*-phosphonomethylglycine (NPMG) are two simpler cases of such compounds in which one methylene carboxylic acid group is replaced by a methylene phosphonic acid group in nitrilotriacetic acid and iminodiacetic acid respectively. Their work also support the polydentate and strong chelating nature of these ligands which have useful applications². Except for one or two binary stability constant determinations^{3,4}, no work has been reported in literature on these ligands involving Be^{II}, Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} ions in different systems.

Results and Discussion

The ligands NPMI and NPMG starts coordinating with the metal ions in pH range of 4.5-5.5. The \bar{n} values from 0.10 to 1.90 indicate the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes and their stabilities are given in Table 1.

In ternary formation systems of Gly, Ala and Cat, the mixed ligand [M-A-L] curves follow those of the 1 : 1 [M-A] binary curves, while in cases of 5-SSA, Oxa, Phen, Bipy and imda, [M-L'-A] curves follow those of [M-L'] curves in the lower pH region until the protons of the primary ligands are neutralised. The divergence of ternary curves from binary ones above this region reveals the formation of ternary complexes in a stepwise manner which is further supported by the non-super imposable nature of the theoretical composite curves⁵. The values of ternary complex formations, log K_T or log K'_T alongwith other related parameters are compiled in Table 2. The numerical values of $\Delta \log K$ or [% R.S.] are used for a quantitative comparison of the relative stabilisation of these ternary systems at a given temperature and ionic strength and are indicative of the extent to which the two ligand in the coordination sphere

of the metal ions mutually influence each other. Larger negative values indicate lesser stabilisation of the ternary complexes. From a knowledge of pK_a s and stability constant values, the distribution of total metal among various metal-ligand species as a function of pH is generated by a computer programme BEST⁶ and a few are illustrated in Figs. 1-4. These calculations also reveal the formation of ternary complexes in a stepwise fashion.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 METAL CHELATES OF NPMI AND NPMG

Metal ion		NPMI				NPMG			
Temp. = 30°, I = 0.10 <i>M</i> (KNO ₃)		St.Con.	−Δ <i>G</i>	−Δ <i>H</i>	Δ <i>S</i>	St.Con.	−Δ <i>G</i>	−Δ <i>H</i>	Δ <i>S</i>
H ⁺	p <i>K</i> ₁	5.85				5.60			
	p <i>K</i> ₂	10.45				10.00			
Be ^{II}	log <i>K</i> ₁	14.09	82	40	138	13.00	75	43	106
	log <i>K</i> ₂	10.69	62	29	107	10.16	59	34	82
	log β ₂	24.78				23.16			
Zn ^{II}	log <i>K</i> ₁	12.94	75	37	126	12.64	73	40	110
	log <i>K</i> ₂	9.40	54	26	93	8.95	52	30	70
	log β ₂	22.34				21.59			
Cd ^{II}	log <i>K</i> ₁	12.63	73	34	130	12.15	70	37	101
	log <i>K</i> ₂	9.65	56	25	100	9.48	55	26	94
	log β ₂	22.28				21.63			
Be ^{II}	log <i>K</i> _T ²		−Δ <i>G</i> _T	−Δ <i>H</i> _T	Δ <i>S</i> _T		−Δ <i>G</i> _T	−Δ <i>H</i> _T	Δ <i>S</i> _T
Zn ^{II}	log <i>K</i> _T ²		20	10	31		16	9	23
Cd ^{II}	log <i>K</i> _T ²		21	10	33		21	9	40
	log <i>K</i> _T ²		18	9	30		15	10	17

Values of *G* and *H* in kJ mol^{−1} and *S* in JK^{−1} mol^{−1}.

Lowering of stabilities of ternary complexes compared to that of binary chelates may be due to the greater destabilisation effect^{5,7} caused by the ligand repulsion in the mixed ligand complexes than that in the binary systems, coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordination sites

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF TERNARY METAL CHELATES OF NPMI AND NPMG WITH OTHER CHELATING AGENTS IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM*

 Temp. = 30°, I = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

System	BeII			ZnII			CdII		
	SC	-DSC	%RS	SC	-DSC	%RS	SC	-DSC	%RS
NPMI-Gly	4.86	1.79	26	3.51	1.49	30	3.33	0.79	19
NPMG-Gly	4.81	1.84	28	3.06	1.94	39	3.22	0.94	23
NPMI-Ala	5.33	1.83	25	3.25	1.75	35	3.47	0.78	18
NPMG-Ala	5.17	1.99	28	3.00	2.00	40	3.44	0.81	19
NPMI-Cat	11.60	1.90	14	8.36	1.17	12	7.35	0.35	45
NPMG-Cat	10.99	2.53	19	8.34	1.20	13	7.20	0.51	7
5-SSA-NPMI	14.62 +0.62	5	11.80	1.09	9	12.89	+0.24	2	
5-SSA-NPMG	12.15	0.85	7	11.18	1.46	12	10.77	1.38	11
Oxa-NPMI	13.59	0.50	4	12.21	0.73	6	11.73	1.13	9
Oxa-NPMG	10.76	2.24	17	10.33	1.31	18	9.90	2.24	18
Phen-NPMI	12.80	0.29	2	12.75	0.19	1	12.38	0.27	2
Phen-NPMG	10.82	2.18	17	12.33	0.31	2	11.42	0.73	6
Bipy-NPMI	13.13	0.96	7	12.63	0.30	2	11.98	0.67	5
Bipy-NPMG	10.81	2.19	16	12.10	0.55	4	11.32	0.83	7
imda-NPMI	12.55	1.54	11	11.40	1.53	12	11.03	1.63	13
imda-NPMG	10.61	2.39	18	10.38	2.26	18	9.74	2.41	20

*SC = Stability constants of ternary complexes; DSC = difference in stability constants of binary and ternary complexes and %RS = percentages of relative stabilisation values.

for the second ligand on the primary complex [M-A] compared to free M^{II} aq. ion⁸. A comparison of these statistical considerations shows that the order of stabilities with respect to 'the other chelating agents' (except Oxa for its low pK_a value) in terms of donor atoms follows as O-O > N-N > N-O-O > N-O, which is accordance with their basicity order and denticity nature, because for a series of similar ligands, the higher the basicity of the ligand, greater is the stability of the complex⁷. Electrostatic attractions between the primary complex and secondary ligand also facilitates the formation of ternary complexes. The sequence of stabilities with respect to metal ions follows as Be^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} and with respect to ligands as NPMI > NPMG, because

 Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for Be^{II}-NPMI-Gly system.

NPMI forms three five-membered ring chelates while NPMG only two^{4,9}.

 Fig. 2. Distribution diagram for Be^{II}-NPMG-Ala system.

Analysis of log K_n values into their component heat and entropy factors is essential to understand fully the factors such as size, shape, electronic structure of the central metal ion and the ligand, the temperature and the composition of the solvents, which influence the stability of a metal complex¹⁰. Since the same has not been reported in literature for NPMI and NPMG, stability constants have been calculated at four different temperatures 20, 30, 40 and 50° at a constant ionic strength of 0.10 M (KNO₃). There is a regular decrease in the values of proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants with increasing temperature. The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS for binary and ternary systems are presented in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. These reactions are spontaneous and exothermic as is evidenced by the negative

TABLE 3—ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS* FOR FORMATION OF 1 : 1 AND 1 : 2 METAL CHELATES OF NPMI AND NPMG

 Temp. = 30°, I = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Metal ion	1 : 1 Complex				1 : 2 Complex			
	-ΔG _e	-ΔH _e	-ΔG _c	-ΔH _c	-ΔG _e	-ΔH _e	-ΔG _c	-ΔH _c
NPMI :								
Be ^{II}	137.44	14.60	54.41	54.41	30.69	11.96	41.40	41.43
Zn ^{II}	34.84	13.58	50.34	50.33	27.50	10.72	37.40	37.13
Cd ^{II}	35.56	13.86	47.94	47.93	29.29	11.42	36.51	36.49
NPMG :								
Be ^{II}	30.27	11.80	55.26	55.25	25.22	9.83	43.83	44.63
Zn ^{II}	31.39	12.24	52.05	52.05	22.60	8.81	39.43	39.43
Cd ^{II}	31.55	12.30	49.06	49.05	27.84	10.85	37.27	37.26

*Values in kJ mol⁻¹.

values of ΔG and ΔH. The positive values of ΔS and a much greater increase in number of particles during the reaction leads to disorderness in the system favouring chelate formation; this also indicates that the water dipoles from the hydration shells of metal ion and carboxylate anion are displaced upon interaction, which are essentially electrostatic in nature. The log K₁ values were found to be higher

than $\log K_2$, indicating that mono-complexes are energetically more favoured over the bis-complexes. In such cases it is more likely that bis-complexes react with free metal ion to form mono-complexes and thus the values of ΔG_r , ΔH_r and ΔS_r could be evaluated¹¹ (Table 1).

Fig. 3. Distribution diagram for Zn^{II}-NPMG-Cat system.

To get an insight into the extent of ionic and covalent nature of the binary and ternary complexes formed, the ΔG and ΔH values have been separated into their corresponding

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND THEIR ELECTROSTATIC AND CRATIC COMPONENTS FOR THE TERNARY SYSTEMS OF Zn^{II} AND Cd^{II} WITH NPMG AND OTHER CHELATING AGENTS

Temp. = 30°. I = 0.10 M (KNO₃)

Ternary system	$-\Delta G$	$-\Delta H$	$-\Delta S$	$-\Delta G_e$	ΔH_e	$-\Delta G_c$	$-\Delta H_c$
Zn ^{II} :							
NPMG-Ala	17.40	14.54	9.43	9.33	3.63	18.18	18.17
Oxa-NPMG	59.93	39.81	66.40	21.75	8.48	48.29	48.29
Phen-NPMG	73.39	47.85	84.29	25.65	9.99	57.85	57.85
Cd ^{II} :							
NPMG-Gly	18.70	17.80	2.97	7.92	3.09	20.78	20.89
5-SSA-NPMG	62.07	43.45	61.45	20.67	8.06	51.51	51.51
Bipy-NPMG	65.67	47.80	65.57	21.57	8.41	54.21	56.21

Values of G and H in KJ mol⁻¹ and S in JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

electrostatic, $\Delta G_e = \nu (\Delta S + R \Delta n \ln 55.5)$, where ν represents a temperature characteristic of the medium (for aqueous medium it is 218 K) and Δn stands for the change in the number of solute particles when the reactants change to products, $\Delta H_e = \{(T-\nu) (\Delta S + R \Delta n \ln 55.5)\}$ and cratic, $\Delta G_c = \{\Delta G - \Delta G_e - \Delta n RT \ln 55.5\}$ and $\Delta H_c = \{\Delta H + \Delta H_e\}$ components as described by Degischer and Nancollas¹² (Tables 3 and 4). Comparison of these values indicates that the cratic parts, ΔG_c and ΔH_c are significantly more negative than the electrostatic parts, ΔG_e and ΔH_e , suggesting that covalent forces are stronger than electro-static forces in these complexes.

Experimental

Ligands NPMI¹³ and NPMG¹⁴ were synthesised by the

reported methods. Catechol, 5-SSA, Oxa, Phen, Bipy, imda, Gly and Ala (A.R.) were used. The proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants of binary and ternary systems

Fig. 4. Distribution diagram for Cd^{II}-5-SSA-NPMI system.

were determined potentiometrically in aqueous medium and the values of \bar{n}_A , pK_a , \bar{n} , pL , $\log K_n$ and $\log K_T$ were calculated by the methods of Irving-Rossotti¹⁵ and Santappa-Ramamoorthy¹⁶. Experiments were carried out at 20, 30, 40 and 50° to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters of both the binary and ternary systems.

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